

The Role of Constraints in Entropy

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We have argued in a previous note that given to two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$, one may take the differentials: $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$ and use these to construct a function G such that $dG=0 = c_1 \sum_i dp(e_i) + c_2 \sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i)$. In other words, only the constraint information is present in this function G . One might ask: Why should such a function G be required and why should it be extremized? We argue that there may be multiple $\{p(e_i)\}$ sets which satisfy the two constraints, but one seeks a unique solution, and the $dG=0$ approach yields the minimal information set.. If $f(e_i) = e_i$, this approach yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

The MB distribution, however, may be obtained using reaction balance: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ ((1)). We ask: How is this approach linked to the above one? In particular, ((1)) is based on physical ideas of two-body reactions, while $dG=0$ using the two constraint differentials seems to be more mathematical.

We argue that $dG=0$ using constraint differentials seems to be a more general approach because ((1)) describes a particular physical example which happens to be consistent with $dG=0$ matching differentials of constraints. It is possible that there are other physical situations which do not use ((1)) (i.e. do not distribute a fixed amount of energy), but still yield the MB distribution. We cite the case of the two level atom in equilibrium with a photon bath at temperature T . Then, one only has two values of e_i , e_0 and e_1 , while in the case of ((1)), one has infinite. The general $dG=0$ based on constraints, however, describes both.

Finally, we consider the Tsallis case, which again is not linked to ((1)) because it does not deal with a distribution of a total amount of energy E . We consider a physical example which shows how one may use the $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ approach to solve this problem as well. Thus, the idea of using entropy seems to be more general than specific methods, which although yielding a correct distribution in a particular case, use equations which only apply to the specific case (e.g. ((1))).

Distribution Based Only on Constraint Information

We start with two basic constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F \quad ((2b))$$

It is known that one may have multiple sets $\{p(e_i)\}$ which satisfy these two constraints. One may, however, ask for a unique set with minimal information. To create such a unique set, one may define a minimum information (entropy) function G such that:

$$dG = 0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i) \quad ((3))$$

In the case of $f(e_i) = e_i$ and $c_1 = -1/T$ and $c_2 = 1$.

$$dG = 0 = \sum_i (-e_i/T) dp(e_i) + \sum_i dp(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

A math solution for G is: $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ with $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. Then:

$$p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad h = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((5))$$

An important point we note here is that: \sum_i may be either a finite or infinite sum and one may obtain the MB distribution for both.

We also note that there are other ways of obtaining the MB distribution, such as reaction balance or maximizing $\ln\{N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!\}$ using Stirling's approximation and the two constraints used above. We ask: How do these compare with the $dG=0$ ((4)) approach?

The Case of Reaction Balance

If one considers a gas with two body interactions which follow:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad \text{with} \quad e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((5))$$

one may derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution by taking \ln of the first equation and matching it to $-1/T$ multiplied by the second equation. This bypasses the need for the $dG=0$ ((4)) approach, but we argue that ((5)) may be a set of conditions which only describe this particular two body collision gas scenario and not other situations, even MB ones. We thus first try to see how ((5)) is linked with $dG=0$ ((4)).

One may note that ((5)) is linked with an infinite set of e_i values and also with the constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. If one takes the differential of the first equation of ((5)) and divides by $p(e_1)p(e_2)$ on the RHS and $p(e_3)p(e_4)$ on the LHS, then:

$$dp_1/p_1 + dp_2/p_2 = dp_3/p_3 + dp_4/p_4 \quad ((6))$$

Consider: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, a general form. Then $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ means that:

$$dF(p_1)/dp_1 dp_1 + dF(p_2)/dp_2 dp_2 = dF(p_3)/dp_3 dp_3 + dF(p_4)/dp_4 dp_4 \quad ((7))$$

Equating ((6)) and ((7)), one has: $1/p = dF/dp$ or $F = \ln(p)$.

In fact, the approach used above links ((5)) with the dG procedure exactly, but it also inherently involves an infinite set of e_i values.

Is it possible to use the $dG=0$ ((4)) approach with a finite set of e_i values such that ((5)) does not hold and still obtain the MB distribution?

The Two Level Atom Case

The two level atom (e_0 and e_1 being the energy levels) in equilibrium with a photon gas at temperature T is well-known in the literature. In such a case, ((5)) does not hold for the atom levels because there is physically no collision of e_0 with e_1 . Photons are absorbed and emitted. One still has: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ ($i=1,2$). Is there a constraint on total energy? If the photons are at a certain temperature T , then it seems that by the ideas of thermodynamics, the atom is constrained to also be at temperature T which means that $p(e_1)$ and $p(e_2)$ must lead to an average energy consistent with the temperature T . In other words, there are again two constraints and their differentials are:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((8))$$

It seems that one may apply the ideas linked with ((4)), but this time to a finite set of e_i . One again has: $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and

$$p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad \rightarrow \quad p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad \text{even though} \quad ((5)) \quad \text{does not hold.} \quad ((9))$$

This example seems to show that the $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ approach is more general than specific equations ((5)) pertaining to a specific physical scenario. The MB distribution appears for both the finite e_i set in the two level atom case and the infinite e_i set in the 2-body collision example.

Tsallis Example

We now consider the Tsallis case. Here, we introduce the constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i = F \quad ((10))$$

It seems that there might be a tendency to view this scenario again using the two body gas collision picture, but it may be linked to a completely different physical scenario. In such a case, ((5)) is not relevant even though the $dG=0$ ((4)) approach still applies. We consider the following picture (which we have presented before). Imagine that there are b types of seeds each of which produces e_i amount of grain and b of each type is planted. Let

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((11))$$

be a constraint, but not with $p(e_i)$ representing the probability to have e_i produced, but with $p(e_i)$ representing the probability that type i survives one day. Physically, introduce the idea that it takes q days for a seed to germinate and that once it does s ($p(e_i)^q$ is the probability) it is guaranteed to yield e_i of wheat. One would at first consider that ((11)) should not hold, i.e the probability for a seed of type 1 to survive a day should be completely independent of type 2 etc. Furthermore, there should be no constraint on the final amount of wheat produced. It is possible, however, that if all seeds are planted in the same ground, then there is a link between

the survival of one and the other and each $p(e_i)$ is not an intrinsic value. In other words, increasing the probability for one type of seed to survive a day, reduces the probability for the others. Furthermore, one has to be careful regarding the meaning of the e_i constraint.

The question which then arises is: What is the meaning of the second equation of ((10))?

Mathematically, using the approach of $dG=0$ ((4)) one has:

$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)^q dh/dp = 1$ yielding the Tsallis distribution.

At first, $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ seems like a kind of average e_i , except that $p(e_i)^q$ is not normalized.

If one considers b types of seed and B seeds of each planted, then the total grain is:

$\sum_i B p(e_i)^q e_i = \text{total grain}$ ((12)) $\text{average grain} = \text{total grain} / (Bb)$

Thus: $\sum_i p(e_i)^q e_i / b = \text{average grain}$ ((13))

((13)), however, is not the same as: $\sum_i e_i \text{probability}(e_i) = \text{average grain}$ which is usually used. Thus, one should not interpret the Tsallis example in the same manner as the Maxwell-Boltzmann two body gas situation, even if $p(e_i)^q$ takes the place of $p(e_i)$ in the constraint equation.

Conclusion

We argue that $dG=0 = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$ is a possible general approach of obtaining a minimal information (entropy) function which provides a unique minimal information set of $\{p(e_i)\}$ given a set of constraints. In particular, we note that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by using $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{ave}}$. We note, however, that there are other ways of obtaining the MB distribution, such as reaction balance. We argue that such specific examples (reaction balance) contain specific equations which may be shown to be consistent with the $dG=0$ differential constraint approach even though these specific equations do not apply to other physical examples, while the overall $dG=0$ approach still might. We give the two energy level atom in equilibrium with a photon bath at temperature T as an example. One again obtains an MB distribution (with a finite set of two energy levels, not the infinite one of $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$). The $dG=0$ approach solves both problems, while $p_1 p_2 = p_3 p_4$ is consistent with the $dG=0$ approach, but cannot be applied to the two energy level atom problem. The Tsallis case is another example which may be solved using $dG=0$ and constraint differentials, but it may not be useful to try to map the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ to the usual $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E(\text{average})$ which applies to a different physical scenario, we argue.